

ABOUT THE SUBJECT AND HISTORY OF PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS

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Abstract. *In this article, the history of the formation and development of Pedagogical diagnostics. In the social policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to create harmony between the individual and the society through the realization of national identity, assimilation of national and universal values, to research the abilities, internal capabilities, and unique individual-psychological characteristics of pupils and students, also mentioned about development.*

Key word: *Pedagogical diagnosis, Karlheinz Ingenkamp, knowledge, Misdiagnosis, individual.*

О ПРЕДМЕТЕ И ИСТОРИИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО ДИАГНОСТИКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается история становления и развития педагогической диагностики. В социальной политике Республики Узбекистан, направленной на создание гармонии между личностью и обществом посредством реализации национальной идентичности, усвоения национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей, исследования способностей, внутренних возможностей и уникальных индивидуально-психологических особенностей учащихся и студенток, также упоминается о развитии.*

Ключевое слова: *Педагогический диагноз, Карлхайнц Ингенкамп, знание, ошибочный диагноз, индивид.*

Diagnostics - in Greek: "dia" means "transparent", "gnosphi" means "knowledge". means) specific information about the organized object or process serves as a general means of obtaining.

The term "pedagogical diagnosis" was first coined by a German scientist in 1968 Introduced to science by Karlheinz Ingenkamp.

Analysis of the spiritual and educational process in society with the help of pedagogical diagnostics and the guaranteed results of education are determined. In diagnosis not only the summarization of the results of education, but also the dynamics of changes in the system are observed, the existing shortcomings are eliminated.

Pedagogical, serving to optimize the educational process Diagnostics is considered an integral part of every planned educational process, and the student to constantly monitor how the material is mastered, educational serves to find a solution to the problem in the process. Pedagogical difficulties arising in the educational process with the help of diagnostics will be studied, and ways to eliminate it will be established.

If the importance of diagnosis (diagnosis) from the point of view of the medical field if we see that the disease, its symptoms and the causes of its origin are correctly identified, as a result of the treatment, it is possible for the patient to recover. A wrong diagnosis does not only destroy the action of the doctor, but also the recovery of the patient. can also reduce the possibility. This is what is said about the health of the body thoughts are just as relevant to mental health. Hence the diagnosis is an activity that requires high skill and responsibility.

It is much easier to diagnose the physical development of a person. One for that after performing a series of exercises, a conclusion can be drawn based on its result.

But it is much more difficult to diagnose mental, spiritual, intellectual and social development difficult. The methods used for this purpose are still quite complex. it cannot be said that it will always give the right result. Learning in pedagogical practice pedagogic-psychologists and teachers are special qualities of personality learn, but depending on these results, to all components of development they are not always able to make a general assessment.

Determining the result in the process of planned and targeted teaching and upbringing Necessity created pedagogical diagnostics. Of course, this is in its essence results are determined by simple pedagogical methods. A number of research scientists (G. Royleke, R. Rollet, K. Leongard, A. Bass, E.Lichko, A. Shmelev) pedagogical diagnosis-"pedagogical activity". the process of obtaining information necessary for facilitation.

H. Feger, N. Petillon, V. Bogatskyi "...pedagogical diagnostic psychological separated from diagnosis" - they put forward the opinion. Development theories of pedagogical diagnostics can be divided into 3 periods. The first period, based on the views of ancient scholars, continued until the 21st century the period of advanced research theories. This period can be called a philosophical-literary period. In this period, to study the problems related to the moral and social nature of a person the main attention was paid.

That is why the initial definitions of a person had a much broader meaning. In this definition, what applies to the human personality is his biology, psychology, behavior, culture, spirituality, etc. were included. Second period. From the end of the 19th century to the second half of the 20th century does it include continuation.

That is, during this period, pedagogues develop their personality It is the period that contributed to learning and research. Because it is During this period, investigations were carried out to study the human personality in clinical conditions. In particular, in this period, introversion refers to the individual, that is, his inner self Immerse yourself in your problems and pay attention to the events around you decrease), extroversion, that is, the environment that surrounds a person, the mind to the environment focused and preoccupied with it, the loss of attention to oneself), It is known that excitement is a characteristic of a person with a high level of excitement feelings of fear and excitement, rigidity in psychological and social situations (inhibition of thinking, i.e. judgment or thinking once received and the difficult situation of abandoning the method of movement) inhibition (to the instigators weakening of countermovement), waking state (under the influence of stimuli such as a high level of excitement and its traces remaining for a certain time). psychological conditions were studied.

But during this period, the positive feelings of the person, abilities, cultural, spiritual, and a number of similar qualities diagnosis did not develop. Criticism of a number of scientists who defined pedagogical diagnostics by K. Klauer under it, expresses the following opinion: "Pedagogical diagnosis (diagnosis) it is difficult to perform tasks at the same time.

Pedagogical diagnostics from a set of attempts to make an actual pedagogical decision, verdict consists of Russian scientist V. I. Zverev: "Pedagogical diagnosis is a different pedagogy situational learning, identification of the diversity of the participants of the educational system it is a process of knowing the level of abilities3", - puts forward the opinion. Another Russian scientist, L. Denyakina: » Pedagogical diagnostics is a pedagogue's determining individual-

qualification qualities in the diagnosis of the educational process, help in the creative development of the individual, the success of the pedagogical team is an increasing activity. Pedagogical diagnosis of the effectiveness of the educational process it is used for improvement, content enrichment and attestation" - he writes. As we can see, the term pedagogical diagnosis today has many rates are found. Summarize all the descriptions and comment as follows It is possible: pedagogical diagnosis-pedagogical personality and communication with him to study and analyze the results of the introductory pedagogical system, is the process of improving efficiency. must understand the importance of the goal.

The essence of education is different there are theories. Increase education (teachers, coaches, parents) the most common understanding is that it affects children. Adults in this in accordance with the ideals, goals, tasks, norms, requirements that he considers correct influence is taken into account, of course.

This understanding of education is close to reality, however, it is one-sided and reflects only a certain part of the educational process makes In giving such a definition of education, the object is focused on the influence of adults on the child considered only as "The main goal of pedagogical diagnosis is initiative and if it refers to the education of an independent person, it is to the student gives the role of an active subject in the pedagogic process". So it's continuous spiritual and moral, intellectual and other qualities of the participants of the educational system For diagnosis, it is necessary to study advanced pedagogical experience.

Foreign scientists: Ingo Hartmann, Karlheinz Ingenkamp, Linert, Fricke, Luhmann, Rorschach, Diederich, Heginger, Bachmeir (Germany); Bolsho, Burke, Rollet, Royleke (England); George Fisher, James Rice, T. Stone (Amenka); A. V. Mudrik, V. D. Semyonova, G. N. Filova, S. D. Smirnov, I. V. Dubrovina, Y. Langmeyer, G. M. Breslav, L. P. Fridman, I. Rogov (Russia) issues of pedagogical diagnostics in the educational system researched.

The formation of views on pedagogical diagnostics in Uzbekistan.

The development of pedagogical diagnostics in the 20th century. Pedagogical in Uzbekistan diagnostics is one of the new fields of science with its own history. in 1991 of pedagogical diagnostics after our country gained independence wide opportunities were created for its development. Educational work in our society intellectual development of young people in the organization, increasing their intellectual potential, they have love for the Motherland, national pride, communication etiquette, Uzbek and so on as high as understanding and honoring world culture, art, and national monuments great attention was paid to the formation of human virtues.

Especially 1997 Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and Personnel After the adoption of the National program of training, pedagogical diagnosis and education it is important in increasing the efficiency of the educational process, in evaluating the quality of education is taking a leading place in solving educational tasks. Scientists of our republic: E. Ghaziyev, G'. Shoumarov, M. Kuronov, O. Torayeva, R. MavlonovaO. Musurmonova's spiritual image of youth formation, development and national independence in the consciousness of every member of the society study of issues of inculcating ideas, creating ideological immunity and their scientific and practical schools to find solutions to these problems managed to create.

Today, Professor E. Ghaziyev's "Student in the higher education system diagnosing mental abilities of my student", M. Kuronov's "To the mind of YOUTH such as inculcating ideas of national independence and creating ideological immunity The pedagogy of our society is making

good use of the methodology. Uzbek scientists - B. Kadirov, O. Hasanboyeva, Sh. A. Abdullayeva, K. Determining the professional competence of Zaripov, Qurbaniyozova teachers, Diagnosing the level of upbringing of the young person, whether there is a behavioral defect correcting, adolescent and adolescent students should choose a profession conducted scientific research on the issues of orientation and special methods managed to create and the science of pedagogical diagnostics in Uzbekistan contributed to its formation as Today, B. Kadirov's "Talents and abilities of students diagnosis", O. Hasanboyeva's "Little school-age student Diagnosing abilities", K. Zaripov's "Professional readiness of my teacher diagnosis", SH.A. Abdullayeva's "The level of upbringing of your adolescent methods of diagnosis and correction of behavioral defects is implemented in the continuous education system and gives effective results.

Uzbek scientists - R.H. Djurayev, J.G'. Yoldoshev, B. Khodjayev, Diagnosing the professional activity of the heads of D. Roziyeva's educational institutions, conducting scientific research on the issues of monitoring the quality of education they went Economic and social changes taking place in our country, formation of the economy in an innovative direction, to the world economy integration of quality education, which is one of the urgent issues before the educational system sets the task of implementation and training of quality specialists. Of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on August 15, 2017 "Five priorities for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 Strategy of Actions in the direction of the new content in the country the task of creating a continuous education system was set, with new content in its composition and the formation of an essentially innovative educational system as the main direction was determined.

These are not only management problems, but also subjects of the educational process improvement of technologies of innovative organization of activities, due to diagnosis defines the tasks of doing and learning. So, it is innovative in the education system One of the first steps in organizing the process is to be an innovative teacher diagnosing readiness for the pedagogical process, setting goals, planning, etc is to provide learning of forecasting processes. This condition is a pedagogic diagnosis (self-diagnosis), parents, pedagogues diagnose the student body by; resources, authorized specialists and research carried out by methodologists of education departments also covers directions.

The meaning of the concepts of "activity" and "activity" in the development of a person incomparable. Great people work tirelessly to achieve excellence in their fields those who did. A person can achieve high results with his effort and activity, it is necessary to work on oneself in order to realize abilities and talents. Thus, it is pedagogical in the rational organization of the educational process diagnosis:

- firstly, facilitating the process of individual education;
- secondly, based on the demand of the society, the results of education in advance provide prediction, determination of effectiveness;
- thirdly, to correctly choose a specific educational direction and specialty will help.

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